

Effects of Snowfall on Solar Power Generation

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Acronyms

UAF	University of Alaska Fairbanks
W	watt
MW	megawatt
AC	alternating current
kWh	kilowatt-hour
PV	photovoltaic
F	Fahrenheit
hr	hour

Abstract

This study aimed to determine the economic feasibility of actively clearing snow from a 1-MW array of 4,200 solar panels on the University of Alaska Fairbanks (UAF) campus. This was achieved by building a test array of eight panels, four of which were used as a control, while the remaining four were actively cleared. The snow depth, general weather observations, and total time spent on site were recorded daily during the study period. Based on this information, labor costs and the energy values of the uncleared and cleared panels were estimated. From the assumptions and simplifications made in this study, the additional energy value generated from actively clearing snow from a 4,200-panel solar array (\$18,785.94) does not justify the labor cost required to perform this task (\$49,183.75).

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1 Introduction

This project was developed in response to an interest in installing solar panel arrays at the University of Alaska Fairbanks campus. In winter, structures in Fairbanks are often covered in snow. A solar panel covered with snow would not generate any power; however, solar power generation levels at high latitudes, such as at Fairbanks, would be very low during winter months, even in the absence of snow cover. Therefore, this project aims to determine whether actively removing snow from solar panels is economically viable. A proposal is currently being considered to install a 1 MW solar array on the hillside south of the Butrovich Building on the UAF campus. The present study sought to quantify the costs in lost power due to snow cover on the panels and compare this to the costs of assigning personnel to keep them clear.

Fairbanks is centrally located in a low-lying river valley at an altitude of 141 meters. The area is characterized by a continental sub-arctic climate with relatively warm summers and very cold winters. The mean annual air temperature (1980-2014) is below the freezing point at 27.9°F, with large annual temperature variations from -50 °F to 90 °F (National Weather Service). Fairbanks is sheltered by the Alaska range to the south and the Brooks range to the north, which restricts the advection of moist air, leading to low annual precipitation (Wendler and Shulski).

The study period (November 2013–March 2014) may have been atypical in terms of the seasonal weather patterns in Fairbanks. In October and November 2013, the average temperatures were 11.9 °F and 3.5 °F, respectively, above the long-term mean (Thoman). A total snowfall of 48.1 inches was recorded for the 2013/14 season, compared with the 30-year average of 62.3 inches (The Alaska State Climate Center).

The main components of the system used in this study were two arrays of four simulated panels. The panels were mounted facing due south at an angle of 70° measured from the horizontal. The panels were covered with plastic sheeting to simulate the friction and adhesion properties of a smooth solar panel. A broom, shovel, and snow blower were acquired for snow clearing. A temperature sensor and data logger were mounted on one panel of each array. A timer was used for every observation/clearing session to record the startup time and the time spent clearing the panels.

After the first few snow-clearing events, the snow blower was found to be unnecessary for this project, given the limited number of arrays and the consistency of the snow. However, when clearing a large set of arrays, a snow blower would be recommended to minimize the required clearing time. To achieve a realistic estimate, the rows of panels were walked after each snowfall to simulate clearing them. Most of the time required to maintain the panels was due to clearing the trails to, from, and around the panels.

2 Experimental Setup

The dimensions of the panels used here were chosen to be close to those of standard, commercially available 240 W solar panels. Fairbanks is located at a latitude of 66°N , requiring a fairly steep pitch for mounting solar panels. Throughout the winter, the sun is located at a low elevation in Fairbanks. To maximize exposure averaged across a full year, a fixed inclination angle of 70° was chosen.

Figure 1. Schematic of panels including dimensions (inches)

Figure 2. 3D model of panel

The panels were constructed using readily available supplies from local home improvement retailers for ease, low cost, and effective simulation of real solar panels. The frame of each panel was constructed using 2"x4" lumber, while a plywood deck was used to simulate the collection face of the panel. The smooth surface of the solar panel was simulated using plastic sheeting. Within each array, two panels were selected for active clearing, while the other two were left as a control. This configuration was chosen to establish how much time each pair of panels spent covered with snow and how much power they would have otherwise generated.

Figure 3. Photo of panel construction (Photo credit: Daisy Huang)

Item	Cost	Justification
Plywood framing and plastic sheets for eight simulated solar panels	\$300	To simulate solar panels
Mounting hardware—screws, brackets, etc	\$100	To simulate solar panels
Shovels, brooms, other manual clearing equipment	\$100	To clear snow
Temperature loggers	\$200	To monitor the amount of time the panels are covered with snow
Stopwatch	\$20	To measure the labor time spent clearing the snow
Total	\$920	

Table 1. Materials, approximate cost, and purpose

Snow accumulation was measured on a semi-weekly basis, typically in response to a period of snowfall. The data collected included the date of the recording, the daily high and low temperatures, the depth of snow on the uncleared panel, startup time in preparation for clearing the panels, the time spent clearing the panels, and notes on the procedure and weather. The maximum and minimum temperatures were initially recorded from the National Weather Service. The temperatures recorded after December 16, 2013, were taken from the thermocouples installed on the panels. The temperature loggers recorded one data point every hour. The solar radiation and AC energy generation were estimated using a performance calculator for grid-connected PV systems provided by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory.

3 Discussion

To determine the cost differences between the cleared and uncleared panels, the combined operating and labor costs were compared with the annual power generation values based on estimates from the collected data. The time taken to clear the panels was logged on a day-to-day basis throughout the study. Time spent shoveling paths and time spent actually clearing panels were logged separately, so that both times could be extrapolated differently to estimate how long it would take to keep the panels cleared. The total time spent clearing the four experimental panels over the course of the study was 3.208 hours. The proposed solar array is 1 MW, which would require 4,200 of the simulated 240 W panels. For an array of 4,200 panels, the required maintenance time would be 3,368.75 hours. Assuming a salary of \$14.60/hr, the total labor cost for this maintenance duration would be \$49,183.75. Other potential costs of hiring or reassigning employees to snow clearing, such as healthcare, transportation, etc., were disregarded for these calculations.

	Preparation time (hours)	Active clearing time (hours)	Total
4 panels	2.55	0.658	3.208
4,200 panels	2677.5	691.25	3368.75
Labor cost	\$39,091.50	\$10,092.25	\$49,183.75

Table 2. Required clearing time and labor costs for solar arrays containing four and 4,200 panels.

The daily energy value was determined by multiplying the estimated amount of AC energy generated by the university's electricity cost, which was \$0.2057 per kWh in September 2014 (FS Utility Billing Manager). This value was then multiplied by the measured visibility on each studied day. The visibility was assigned a value of zero during overcast or snowing conditions, a value of 0.5 if the weather was partially cloudy and there was sufficient sunlight for power generation, and a value of 1.0 if conditions were completely clear. The calculated values are for one 240 W solar panel. The calculations presented here only consider the energy value over the studied period. The control panel was calculated to generate an energy value of \$116.72, which is equivalent to \$490,234.55 for an array of 4,200 panels. The actively cleared panel was calculated to generate an energy value of \$121.20, which corresponds to a value of \$509,020.49 for an array of 4,200 panels. Accordingly, actively clearing a 4,200-panel array would generate an additional energy value of \$18,785.94 relative to the uncleared control panels.

	Energy value of actively cleared panel (\$)	Energy value of control panel (\$)	Value gained from clearing (\$)
1 panel	\$121.20	\$116.72	\$4.47
4,200 panels	\$509,020.90	\$490,234.55	\$18,785.94

Table 3. Energy value comparison between actively cleared and control panels

The total amount of time spent clearing the four experimental panels over the study period (both preparation and actual clearing) was 192.5 minutes. For an array of 4,200 panels, this would equate to a maintenance time of 3,368.75 hours. Assuming a salary of \$14.60/hr, the labor for this period would be valued at \$49,183.75.

4 Conclusions

This study was conducted to determine the costs and benefits of clearing a solar array of accumulated snow versus leaving the panel unattended throughout the winter. By analyzing the obtained data in the context of 2014 energy costs, it was determined that the cleared panels would have generated an additional \$18,785.94 in electricity relative to the uncleared panels, representing a monetary gain of 3.7%. However, based on the estimated labor times and an assumed hourly rate, it would have cost \$49,183.75 to keep 4,200 panels clear throughout the winter. The costs of manually clearing the panels would exceed the value of electricity generated by the solar panels by over \$30,000 based on the assumptions and simplifications in this study.

These results confirm that leaving the panels uncleared and allowing them to shed snow naturally would be the optimal course of action. The snow this past winter (November 2013 to March 2014) proved to be low in water density, despite the unusually high temperatures. Snow that was not cleared by hand usually shed naturally within a few days due to subsequent winds and solar heating.

To provide more realistic cost estimates, other factors should be considered. For example, the costs involved in transporting workers to and from the site would increase the cost of clearing the panels. In addition, the cost of the clearing equipment was not taken into account. Incorporating these factors would further widen the gap between the costs and benefits of snow clearing.

The outcomes of this study form part of a broader analysis of the proposed solar array on the UAF campus. This study was limited in scope; therefore, factors such as construction costs and UAF's sustainability pledge were excluded from the analysis.

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Appendix A Supplemental Information

Table A.1. Date, temperature, and weather notes

Date	Minimum temperature °F	Maximum temperature °F	Weather notes
11/3/2013	-4	-2	First big snow storm of the season; appx 3 inches of accumulation. Panels not completely built yet; skies were overcast.
11/12/2013	-17	-12	light snow, overcast
11/13/2013	-12	5	Ice/snow storm prior night and this morning; I'm not sure whether panels will be clearable. Heavy to moderate snowfall following morning freezing rain.
11/14/2013	-15	2	Winds 30-60 km/hr. Moderate to light snowfall, Freezing rain last night.
11/15/2013	-15	-10	Light overcast, no snow.
11/16/2013	-25	-7	Overcast, light snow in the late evening.
11/17/2013	-20	-17	Overcast. Light snow.
11/18/2013			Overcast, light snow.
11/19/2013	-9	-25	mostly cloudy, no snow
11/20/2013	-31	-23	Foggy, no snow.
11/21/2013	-24	-18	Light fog, mostly clear.
11/22/2013	2	17	overcast
11/23/2013	5	17	mostly cloudy, no snow
11/24/2013	-7	13	mostly cloudy, no snow
11/25/2013	2	13	Light snow, partly cloudy
11/26/2013	-21	-13	Mostly overcast during the day, clearing off at night.
11/27/2013	-6	5	Mostly overcast, light snow
11/28/2013	-18	5	Mostly overcast, light snow
11/29/2013	-18	-4	Mostly overcast, light snow
11/30/2013	-28	-8	partly cloudy
12/1/2013	-28	-18	mostly cloudy, no snow
12/2/2013	-23	-18	mostly cloudy, no snow
12/3/2013	-7	10	overcast
12/4/2013	-11	10	mostly cloudy, no snow
12/5/2013	-4	24	mostly cloudy, light freezing rain
12/6/2013	15	25	overcast
12/7/2013	15	29	mostly cloudy
12/8/2013	20	32	overcast, light snow
12/9/2013	26	32	light snow, overcast
12/10/2013	0	27	partly cloudy
12/11/2013	-3	9	clear
12/12/2013	2	5	overcast
12/13/2013	-23	-16	Windy, mostly clear.
12/14/2013	2	5	Windy, mostly cloudy
12/15/2013	-21	-2	light snow
12/16/2013	-36	-23	Partly cloudy. Cold.
12/17/2013	-32	-22	light snow
12/18/2013	-25	-11	Cloudy
12/19/2013	-22	-15	light snow, cloudy
12/20/2013	-18	-14	mostly cloudy

Table A.2. Date, temperature, and weather notes

Date	Minimum temperature °F	Maximum temperature °F	Weather notes
12/21/2013	-17	-10	light snow, mostly cloudy
12/22/2013	-16	-11	light snow
12/23/2013	-14	-21	4-6 inches of snow have fallen over the prior several days.
12/24/2013	-31	-10	Clear sky, no wind
12/25/2013	-36	-15	Clear sky, no wind
12/26/2013	-39	-15	clear sky, light winds
12/27/2013	-38	-12	clear sky, light winds
12/28/2013	-28	-16	clear sky, light winds
12/29/2013	-22	-15	clear sky, light winds
12/30/2013	-22	-5	clear sky, light winds
12/31/2013	-21	0	clear sky, light winds
1/1/2014	-14	8	clear sky, light winds
1/2/2014	-19	-13	overcast with light snow showers in patches
1/3/2014	-15	-9	overcast with no snowfall
1/4/2014	-15	-7	overcast with light snow showers
1/5/2014	-8	-4	overcast with light snow showers
1/6/2014	-11	-6	overcast with no snowfall
1/7/2014	-14	-10	overcast with no snowfall
1/8/2014	-12	-9	overcast with no snowfall
1/9/2014	-19	-11	overcast with light snow showers
1/10/2014	-28	-17	partly cloudy. Cold.
1/11/2014	-33	-11	clear sky, light winds
1/12/2014	-38	-9	clear sky, light winds
1/13/2014	-38	-19	light snow
1/14/2014	-25	-11	overcast with light snow showers
1/15/2014	-21	-15	overcast with no snow showers
1/16/2014	-14	-8	overcast with light snow showers
1/17/2014	-10	9	overcast with no snow showers
1/18/2014	-14	-7	overcast with light snow showers
1/19/2014	-15	4	partly cloudy
1/20/2014	-10	0	mostly cloudy
1/21/2014	-4	22	mostly cloudy
1/22/2014	-3	1	Mostly cloudy. Light snow. Light breeze.
1/23/2014	-1	12	cloudy, briefly rained
1/24/2014	-3	28	slightly cloudy
1/25/2014	-3	28	partly cloudy
1/26/2014	-3	14	slightly cloudy
1/27/2014	-5	28	partly cloudy
1/28/2014	-8	27	slightly cloudy
1/29/2014	-13	25	cloudy
1/30/2014	-17	21	cloudy
1/31/2014	-19	12	slightly cloudy
2/1/2014	-16	-6	cloudy
2/2/2014	-12	16	light snow
2/3/2014	-13	25	sunny, clear
2/4/2014	-16	17	partly cloudy
2/5/2014	-18	0	rain, light snow
2/6/2014	-14	-6	snow

Table A.3. Date, temperature, and weather notes

Date	Minimum temperature °F	Maximum temperature °F	Weather notes
2/7/2014	-19	8	partly cloudy
2/8/2014	-27	18	partly cloudy
2/9/2014	-32	17	foggy
2/10/2014	-30	16	clear
2/11/2014	-31	4	partly cloudy
2/12/2014	-31	-5	light snow
2/13/2014	-28	-12	mostly cloudy
2/14/2014	-27	17	slightly cloudy
2/15/2014	-22	-10	light snow
2/16/2014	-21	21	Overcast
2/17/2014	-27	25	Post weekend storm 3-4" of snow accumulation. Partly cloudy.
2/18/2014	-22	25	cloudy
2/19/2014	-27	18	mostly cloudy
2/20/2014	-29	7	foggy
2/21/2014	-30	27	clear
2/22/2014	-23	28	slightly cloudy
2/23/2014	-20	42	sunny
2/24/2014	-20	40	sunny
2/25/2014	-22	38	sunny
2/26/2014	-17	30	sunny
2/27/2014	-10	43	sunny
2/28/2014	-11	37	sunny
3/1/2014	-15	35	sunny
3/2/2014	-16	39	sunny
3/3/2014	-18	37	sunny
3/4/2013	-15	10	light snow
3/5/2014	-16	4	light snow
3/6/2014	-18	40	Post 2 day snow. appx 4" accumulation. Mostly clear.
3/7/2014	-22	44	partly cloudy
3/8/2014	-24	31	partly cloudy
3/9/2014	-25	28	sunny
3/10/2014	-25	-2	sunny
3/11/2014	-10	29	sunny
3/12/2014	-16	33	sunny
3/13/2014	-3	39	sunny
3/14/2014	-4	28	sunny
3/15/2014	-18	32	sunny
3/16/2014	-20	25	sunny
3/17/2014	-15	46	sunny
3/18/2014	-10	29	mostly cloudy
3/19/2014	-17	29	light snow
3/20/2014	-18	28	post light snow
3/21/2014	-12	48	partly cloudy
3/22/2014	-15	49	partly cloudy
3/23/2014	-12	52	sunny

Table A.4. Raw data collection and notes

Date	Depth of snow on uncleared panel, measured perpendicular to the panel, cm	Startup time spent before clearing panels (e.g., shoveling paths to the panels, starting up the snow blower), minutes	Time spent clearing the panels, minutes	Other notes
11/12/2013	0	0	0	Panels completely built! Study officially begins today.
11/13/2013			15	Clearing 4 panels on the left, leaving the 4 on the right as a control.
11/14/2013			10	Wind storm knocked down front left panel, which I righted.
11/15/2013			0	5 minutes to check panels, no snow to clear.
11/16/2013			0	5 minutes to check panels, no snow to clear.
11/17/2013			7	7 minutes to clear panels
11/18/2013				
11/19/2013	1.35	25	1	very light dusting of snow on panels, shoveled partial path from parking lot to panel site
11/20/2013	1.35 cm in	2	0.5	Dusted a little frost off the tops of the panels. Most of the snow has patches fallen off the control group panels
11/21/2013	1 cm in patches	1	0	No snow to be cleared.
11/22/2013				
11/23/2013	1.4 cm patches	0	0	Two front control panels were completely clear of snow, two back control panels had patches of snow along bottom. There was no snow to be cleared on the other panels.
11/24/2013				

Table A.5. Raw data collection and notes

Date	Depth of snow on uncleared panel, measured perpendicular to the panel, cm	Startup time spent before clearing panels (e.g., shoveling paths to the panels, starting up the snow blower), minutes	Time spent clearing the panels, minutes	Other notes
11/25/2013	1.5 cm patches	0	1	Light dusting of snow on panels, slightly icy, but otherwise fairly clear.
11/26/2013	3.75 cm in patches	1	0.5	Dusted some snow off the tops of panels, icy frost on fronts of panels.
11/27/2013				
11/28/2013				
11/29/2013				
11/30/2013				
12/1/2013				
12/2/2013				
12/3/2013				
12/4/2013	3.4-3.7cm in patches	1	1	
12/5/2013				
12/6/2013				
12/7/2013				
12/8/2013				
12/9/2013				
12/10/2013				
12/11/2013	2.9 cm	1	1	Front panels clear, slightly icy, Back panels snow in patches
12/12/2013				
12/13/2013	0	60	0	Shoveled path to and around panels. Panels themselves clear. Snow heavily wind transported.
12/14/2013				
12/15/2013				
12/16/2013	0	5	0	Temperature loggers installed. #1 will go on panels being actively cleared (West). #2 will go on control panels (East). They will take 1 data point every hour.
12/17/2013				
12/18/2013				
12/19/2013				

Table A.6. Raw data collection and notes

Date	Depth of snow on uncleared panel, measured perpendicular to the panel, cm	Startup time spent before clearing panels (e.g., shoveling paths to the panels, starting up the snow blower), minutes	Time spent clearing the panels, minutes	Other notes
12/20/2013				
12/21/2013				
12/22/2013				
12/23/2013				Daisy did a drive-by; the "cleared" panels are clear. The "control" panels are partially self-cleared.
12/24/2013				
12/25/2013				
12/26/2013				
12/27/2013				
12/28/2013				
12/29/2013				
12/30/2013				
12/31/2013				
1/1/2014				
1/2/2014				
1/3/2014				
1/4/2014				
1/5/2014				
1/6/2014				
1/7/2014				
1/8/2014				
1/9/2014				
1/10/2014				
1/11/2014				
1/12/2014				
1/13/2014				
1/14/2014				
1/15/2014				
1/16/2014				
1/17/2014				
1/18/2014				
1/19/2014				
1/20/2014				
1/21/2014	2.4 cm in patch	1	0.5	Back panels completely clear of snow, only one panel in front had small patch of snow. Control panels were almost completely clear, one small patch on front left control panel

Table A.7. Raw data collection and notes

Date	Depth of snow on uncleared panel, measured perpendicular to the panel, cm	Startup time spent before clearing panels (e.g., shoveling paths to the panels, starting up the snow blower), minutes	Time spent clearing the panels, minutes	Other notes
1/22/2014	0	5	0	panels self clearing
1/23/2014	0 cm	7	0	panels completely clear (not icy), shoveled path around panels
1/24/2014				
1/25/2014				
1/26/2014	0	1	0	panels completely clear, not icy
1/27/2014				
1/28/2014	0	1	0	panels completely clear, not icy
1/29/2014				
1/30/2014				
1/31/2014	0.2	6	0	hoarfrost
2/1/2014				
2/2/2014				
2/3/2014	0	0	0	panels self clearing
2/4/2014				
2/5/2014				
2/6/2014				
2/7/2014				
2/8/2014				
2/9/2014				
2/10/2014				
2/11/2014				
2/12/2014				
2/13/2014				
2/14/2014				
2/15/2014				
2/16/2014	1.9-3.5	6	2	Shoveled quick path,
2/17/2014	0	25	0	Panels self-cleared of snow. Improved path to and around panels.
2/18/2014				
2/19/2014				
2/20/2014				
2/21/2014				
2/22/2014				
2/23/2014				
2/24/2014				
2/25/2014				
2/26/2014				
2/27/2014				
2/28/2014				

Table A.8. Raw data collection and notes

Date	Depth of snow on uncleared panel, measured perpendicular to the panel, cm	Startup time spent before clearing panels (e.g., shoveling paths to the panels, starting up the snow blower), minutes	Time spent clearing the panels, minutes	Other notes
3/1/2014				
3/2/2014				
3/3/2014				
3/4/2013				
3/5/2014				
3/6/2014	0	5	0	Panels self clearing. Path travels well.
3/7/2014				
3/8/2014				
3/9/2014				
3/10/2014				
3/11/2014				
3/12/2014				
3/13/2014				
3/14/2014				
3/15/2014				
3/16/2014				
3/17/2014				
3/18/2014				
3/19/2014				
3/20/2014	0	0	0	panels self-clearing
3/21/2014				
3/22/2014				
3/23/2014				panels deconstructed

Table A.11. Energy value analysis

Solar radiation (based on PV watts calculator) (kWhr/m ² per day)	AC energy potential (kWhr)	AC energy generated (kWhr)	Visibility (1 for clear, 0 for over-cast)	University energy cost (\$/kWhr)	Solar energy value (\$)	Snow on active panel? (1 for no, 0 for yes)	Snow on control panel? (1 for no, 0 for yes)	Energy value of actively cleared panels (\$)	Energy value of control panels (\$)	Value gained from active clearing (\$)
2.42	13.566	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	0	0	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	0	0	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	0	0	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	0	0	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	0	0	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0	1	\$0.2057	\$2.79	0	0	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	0	0	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	0	0	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	0	0	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	0	0	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	0	0	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	1	0	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	1	1	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	1	1	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	1	1	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	1	1	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	1	1	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	13.566	1	\$0.2057	\$2.79	1	1	\$2.79	\$2.79	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	0		\$0.2057	\$0.00	1	1	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	13.566	1	\$0.2057	\$2.79	1	1	\$2.79	\$2.79	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	13.566	1	\$0.2057	\$2.79	1	1	\$2.79	\$2.79	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	13.566	1	\$0.2057	\$2.79	1	1	\$2.79	\$2.79	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	13.566	1	\$0.2057	\$2.79	1	1	\$2.79	\$2.79	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	13.566	1	\$0.2057	\$2.79	1	1	\$2.79	\$2.79	\$0.00
2.42	13.566	13.566	1	\$0.2057	\$2.79	1	1	\$2.79	\$2.79	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	27.323	1	\$0.2057	\$5.62	1	1	\$5.62	\$5.62	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	27.323	1	\$0.2057	\$5.62	1	1	\$5.62	\$5.62	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	27.323	1	\$0.2057	\$5.62	1	1	\$5.62	\$5.62	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	0	0	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	0	0	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	13.6615	0.5	\$0.2057	\$2.81	1	1	\$2.81	\$2.81	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	13.6615	0.5	\$0.2057	\$2.81	1	1	\$2.81	\$2.81	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	13.6615	0.5	\$0.2057	\$2.81	1	1	\$2.81	\$2.81	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	27.323	1	\$0.2057	\$5.62	1	1	\$5.62	\$5.62	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	27.323	1	\$0.2057	\$5.62	1	1	\$5.62	\$5.62	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	27.323	1	\$0.2057	\$5.62	1	1	\$5.62	\$5.62	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	27.323	1	\$0.2057	\$5.62	1	1	\$5.62	\$5.62	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	27.323	1	\$0.2057	\$5.62	1	1	\$5.62	\$5.62	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	27.323	1	\$0.2057	\$5.62	1	1	\$5.62	\$5.62	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	27.323	1	\$0.2057	\$5.62	1	1	\$5.62	\$5.62	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	27.323	1	\$0.2057	\$5.62	1	1	\$5.62	\$5.62	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	27.323	1	\$0.2057	\$5.62	1	1	\$5.62	\$5.62	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	27.323	1	\$0.2057	\$5.62	1	1	\$5.62	\$5.62	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	27.323	1	\$0.2057	\$5.62	1	1	\$5.62	\$5.62	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	1	1	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	0	0	\$0.2057	\$0.00	0	0	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

Table A.12. Energy Value Analysis

Solar radiation (based on PV watts calculator) (kWhr/m ² per day)	AC energy potential (kWhr)	AC energy generated (kWhr)	Visibility (1 for clear, 0 for over-cast)	University energy cost (\$/kWhr)	Solar energy value (\$)	Snow on active panel? (1 for no, 0 for yes)	Snow on control panel? (1 for no, 0 for yes)	Energy value of actively cleared panels (\$)	Energy value of control panels (\$)	Value gained from active clearing (\$)
4.57	27.323	13.6615	0.5	\$0.2057	\$2.81	1	1	\$2.81	\$2.81	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	13.6615	0.5	\$0.2057	\$2.81	1	1	\$2.81	\$2.81	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	13.6615	0.5	\$0.2057	\$2.81	1	1	\$2.81	\$2.81	\$0.00
4.57	27.323	27.323	1	\$0.2057	\$5.62	1	1	\$5.62	\$5.62	\$0.00